

Research

IMPACT OF REGULATIONS AND POLICIES ON MICROFINANCE SECTOR DEVELOPMENT IN GHANA

Ramatu Ussif¹*, Murat Ertuğrul²

¹Department of Business Administration, Graduate School of Social Sciences, Anadolu University, Eskişehir, Turkey.

²Faculty of Economic and Administrative Sciences. Department of Business Administration, Anadolu University, Eskişehir, Turkey.

*Corresponding author

Ramatu Ussif

ramatussif@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article looks at whether financial regulations and Government policies have an impact on microfinance institutions operations in Ghana. It also looks at contributions that regulations and policies have on microfinance sector development in the country. The methodology for this paper is purely qualitative. The needed information was gathered from primary & secondary sources. The primary data source used face to face interviews, telephonic and through emails conducted with regulators, policymakers and microfinance institutions managers, using interview guide and focus group discussion guide. The secondary source was through literature reviews, books, journals, and the internet. The study revealed that financial regulations and government policies have contributed immensely to microfinance sector development through, training & capacity building, checks and balances, protecting customers and depositors, financial soundness and financial inclusion. However, despite the contribution of regulations and the policies to the sub-sector, the result of the study also identified poor regulations, lack of proper decentralization, lack of knowledge and weakness of regulators as problems with financial regulation. Furthermore, it also found out that, the policies formulated are weak and the implementation, monitoring, and supervision of the institutions is insufficient and ineffective. This article, therefore, recommends that Apex bodies should be involved in monitoring and supervision, minimum capital requirements should be made moderate, powers should be decentralized to the regional level for the effective functioning of regulations & policies in the country.

Keywords: Bank of Ghana, Regulations, Ministry of Finance, Policy Formulation, Microfinance Institutions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rate at which microfinance institutions are increasing in the country gives rise to its regulation. Financial regulation is an important tool in every financial institution across the world. There is the need for a proper consensus and understanding of the formulation, implementation, review of the regulatory framework, government policies, procedures, and processes to ensure consistency, and effective approaches to different types of microfinance regulations in the country. It is crucial for the regulatory and supervisory authority of microfinance institutions to have sufficient knowledge of microfinance institutions' operations to be able to formulate good policies and an appropriate regulatory framework. The Government should have a good policy on the microfinance sub-sector and there should be a review on the laws, rules and other legislative bodies for it not to be rigid. The main reason for regulation in Ghana is for depositors' protection, provide information, ensuring soundness of the financial system, the stability of the sector, and reducing operational risk affecting the operations of the institutions' activities. There is the need to bring together all sectors providing financial services and their clients together, for adequate information provision, depositor/customers fund protection, the assets of the institutions, and proper regulations of the market. Ghana microfinance institutions like most of the other African Countries lacks effective regulations and supervision.

The regulatory framework and supervisory systems seem not functioning and these affect their innovativeness, outreach, building customer base and the general performance of the institutions. The Apex bodies of microfinance institutions consisting of Credit Unions Association (CUA), Association of financial non-governmental organizations (ASSFIN), the Ghana cooperative susu collectors Association (GCSCA), the cooperatives made up the sector and all these bodies in one way or the other are affecting the performance, sustainability, outreach, profitability, growth, and functioning of the sub-sector. Regulations of the sector and the policies implemented by the government ministries towards the effective management of the microfinance sub-sector is a key and crucial aspect of every financial system to ensure long term sustainability.

The objectives of this article is to discuss the "impact of financial regulations and government policies on microfinance sector development by assessing the positive impacts of regulations and policies on microfinance institutions operations in Ghana, examining the negative impacts of regulations and policies on microfinance institutions operations in Ghana, expatiating the role of government policies towards microfinance institutions operations and development and finally, investigating the objective of government policies towards microfinance institutions.

1.1 Regulations in Ghana and other Countries

The Bank of Ghana in August 2011 came up with some regulatory and operational guidelines for the MFIs in the country. The institution is solely regulated by the Bank of Ghana. The guidelines were prudential and non-prudential and do not address the financial soundness of the institutions fully in the country. The microfinance sub-sector needs effective regulatory instruments for effective prudential regulation, monitoring, and supervision in the country. A critical analysis of the policies and the regulatory guidelines will help to understand the advantages and disadvantages of this institution which can affect the microfinance sub-sector and also defeat the objectives and visions of the microfinance institution in the country. There is a need for effective regulations and efficient policymaking body for the sector. The unsustainability and collapse rate of microfinance institutions in Ghana calls on for regulations and supervision to protect the customers and their savings. This is because the clients' protection is very important and has a lot of implications.

Microfinance is fast moving from a niche product to a worldwide recognized form of finance. There is a need to regulate banking institutions and non-bank financial institutions in a country. In Ghana the sole regulator of microfinance institutions is the Bank of Ghana and they came out with regulatory and operational guidelines for microfinance institutions. The guidelines which are prudential and non-prudential do not seem fully to address the soundness of the microfinance subsector in Ghana. Regulations of financial markets is crucial and customer protection is one of the important factors in the microfinance sector. Arysad (2005) on their study microfinance institutions performance and sustainability in Indonesia using a village credit institution as a case study, found out that, an economy which is growing and supported by government policies in all part of their operations by providing a legal root for the institutions has a high performance and continues sustainability.

The bank of Ghana regulations in the country had contributed towards the benefits and successes of microfinance institutions. There is the need for appropriate regulations of the subsector in the country and it should be supported by effective government policies to monitor and supervise the institutions to ensure long term sustainability and reduce collapse rate in the sector. This regulation and policy-making of the markets call for the active participation of government & regulators in the microfinance industry. The regulators believe that to protect the customers and their savings, the interest rate should be capped and transparency promoted.

Pouchous (2012) said most of the microfinance management and professionals are against such practices. They are of the view that the policymakers may not be able to come out with an appropriate interest rate cap which will help the development, sustainability, growth, and survival of microfinance institutions in Ghana which intend to jeopardize the services of the financial inclusion to the poor customers (Helms & Reille, 2004). Regulators can only through the regulatory requirements take account of microfinance loan pricing to protect the poor customer against harm and higher prices for this implies the macro level. This was the reason for the government intervention because the macroeconomic disruptions can have a consequence on financial institutions of the country as a whole. According to Arun & Murinde (2010), the main purpose of regulating the microfinance institution is to ensure the efficiency, soundness, smoothness, and stability of financial services, and to protect the consumers. Thus no activity of the institution should harm the clients and the regulations not to affect the activities of the microfinance institution.

1.2 Some African Countries Experiences

The below indicate the experiences of other countries with their regulatory body/bodies.

1.2.1 Kenya's Experience

Kenya is one of the countries in African doing well with microfinance in the world. The Kenyan microfinance institution is registered under eight different parliamentary Act which includes:

- The act of Non-Governmental Organizations and Co-ordination
- The act of building societies
- The act of the Trustee
- The Act of Societies
- The Act of the Co-operative Societies
- The Act of Companies
- The Banking Act, and
- The Act of Kenya Post Office Savings Bank (KPOSB)

The legal structures guiding the microfinance institutions in Kenya are also of different types and this makes the regulations of the sector complicated. Due to the above, Omino (2005) concluded that some of the above-mentioned forms of registrations refuse to address the issues regarding accountability, governance, and ownership and also pave the way for poor performance

and collapse of the microfinance institutions. This came about as a result of the poor regulatory framework.

1.2.2 Uganda's Experience

Regulations of a microfinance institution in Uganda started in 2004 but the law of deposit-taking microfinance institution thus, (MDI Act, 2003) law was enacted by the parliament s in 2003. This law ignores all microfinance institutions that do not take deposits and recognizes all those mobilizing deposits. The Ugandan regulations' primary role is to promote a strong and viable microfinance industry to enhance economic development and growth by helping reducing poverty in the rural & urban communities of the country. Also, help promote the growth of the Ugandan financial sector by ensuring microfinance institutions businesses are conducted safely and soundly. Again, the credit institutions operating in the country are regulated under the financial institutions Act of 2004. While other Commercial Banks undertaking microfinance activities are also regulated under the same law.

1.2.3 Malawi's Experience

In 2002, the Malawian government passed a microfinance policy and action plan. This policy was similar to the Ghana Microfinance Policy (GHAMP). The policy aims at creating a sound environment that would facilitate and encourage the adoption of universally acknowledge best practices through microfinance. Microfinance institutions in Malawi is currently regulated through a legislative instrument. While the non-governmental organizations (NGOs) registered under the Act of trustees' incorporation. Private sector microfinance companies registered under the Companies Act and the SACCOs are also registered under the Act of cooperative Societies and because most of the institution's instruments are not in the jurisdiction of the Malawian reserve bank, it becomes difficult to administer them.

1.2.4 Egypt's Experience

The microfinance institution in Egypt is regulated under different authorities depending upon the legal identification of the sub-sector. For example, the central bank of Egypt like that of Ghana is the prudential and sole regulator of the banks in Egypt while the ministry of solidarity is the regulator of microfinance that is non - governmental. Furthermore, the social fund for development is in charge of coordinating and planning the microfinance institutions as designated by the law. In Egypt, all microfinance institutions that mobilize deposits and those willing to mobilize deposits have to transform into formal financial institutions.

1.3 Microfinance Policies and Programs in Ghana

The microfinance policies and programs of the government within the country are targeted towards achieving the aims and objectives of the microfinance sector in the country. These policies are being carried out by the ministry of finance and the duties of the sector are policy formulation and implementation of the institutions. This department work in collaboration with the financial regulatory body from bank of Ghana and the various microfinance institutions not excluding the key apex bodies of microfinance and other key stakeholders within and outside the country.

1.3.1 The Rational for Microfinance Policy in Ghana

The microfinance sector started operation in Ghana in the 1970s. Since its operations, there has not been any policy guideline nor goal for the institution and this slows down the growth and progress of the microfinance sector. Though the government has involved in microfinance in those times yet still could not come out with an appropriate policy framework. These indeed post a lot of problems and issues to the sector including slow growth, no proper direction, lack of coordination and fragmentation and there was no effective and coherent process and procedure to deal with these challenges the institutions are faced with. Some of the challenges the microfinance is facing include ineffective regulations, poor coordination & collaboration, inadequate capacity building, institutional linkages are weak, lack of skills and experiences, and low level of education. To integrate the microfinance sector into a better one with overall financial sector development, there should be proper coordination and collaboration between the key stakeholders thus, the government, ministries, departments, agencies, donors, development partners, owners, management, employees, investors, and the customers.

Again microfinance helps in financing small and medium enterprises because the sector has not been favored by activities of traditional/conventional banks in the country. This is due to the differences in the procedures involved in credit issuing and others. The commercial banks need long procedure that requires documentary evidence, collateral security, guarantors, long-standing queues and bank customer relationships which the small and medium enterprises does not require. Also, the formal institutions in Ghana have a diversified supervised regulatory framework which is been licensed by bank of Ghana and not the informal sector. This raised the issue of concern for the appropriate regulatory framework to also be extended to other institutions like the microfinance to improve outreach, delivery of credit, savings, sustainability, and institutional arrangements. The above reasons informed the development of the microfinance policy in Ghana.

1.4 Ghana Microfinance Policy Framework

The main aim and goal of the Ghana microfinance policy is to enhance and promote the efficient delivery and sustainability of the institutions' products and services to help achieve the purpose of it to reduce poverty and wealth creation within the scope of the poverty reduction objective of Ghana, the developmental strategies, and growth of financial sector.

1.4.1 Microfinance Policy Objective

The primary objective of the microfinance policy includes:

- Creating an enabling environment both at the micro & macro levels which would help microfinance institutions operations in the country.
- Help in providing facilities for the growth and sustainable fund flow, providing adequate infrastructure, human resources, and capital development.
- Ensuring that the microfinance sub-sector is harmonized and well-coordinated in the country.
- Ensuring a very sustainable and integrated institution through poor and low-income individuals.
- Facilitating programs and activities that ensures the protection of customer/consumers.

1.4.2 Strategies to Achieve Goals and Objectives of the Policies

For the above goals and objectives of the microfinance policy to be achieved in the country, the below strategies were adopted by the government and the policy formulation and implementation department at the ministry of finance.

- Effective institutional arrangements and well coordination and collaboration institutions.
- Building capacity of all the staffs of the sub-sector through intensive and compulsory training.
- Qualitative financial services delivery and intensive and efficient management within the institutions.
- Classifying target groups of the poor and low-income people, people with vulnerability and the marginalized people.
- Protection of customer and small depositors' funds, and the entire consumers.
- Free flow of information, efficient data gathering, and proper information dissemination
- Consistent regulation, a good regulatory framework for the institution and supervision

- Researching, monitoring the institutions, and evaluation of the performance of the institutions.

1.4.2.1 Institutional Arrangements, Coordination and Collaboration

There should be coordination and collaboration among the key stakeholders of the microfinance institution. The government, donors, policy makers, regulators, managers, employees, development partners and other should all act responsively, together in a peaceful, coherent and very sustainable manner so as to help build a strong microfinance sub sector. When this happens, there shall be a well-coordinated, collaborated and well defined institutional arrangements indicating and spelling out the roles, responsibilities and functions of the key stakeholders. Through proper coordination and collaboration between all the institutions, errors will be reduced within the sub sector and it will foster a complementary of various activities within the industry by all the key stakeholders

1.4.2.2 Capacity Building

For an effective and efficient microfinance sub-sector to be developed, a very well human capital program must be developed. There should also be a good infrastructural development and a sufficient source of funding. Capacity building in the microfinance sector is very important and it involves the above three factors/strategic areas thus, infrastructure, human capital, and funding. When all the above is available, the institutions will be sustainable and able to serve its purpose.

1.4.2.3 Financial Services Delivery and Management

Every successful microfinance sector needs diversified, sustainable effective and efficient financial services delivering and good management. Taking note of a credit delivery system of microfinance institutions such as having a loan, rates of interest, repayments and addressing them properly is vital to the institution's operations. The categorization of the MFIs and the grouping of beneficiaries and potential beneficiaries all are key to organizations' operations.

1.4.2.4 Consumer Protection

The consumers of microfinance institutions shall be protected. The actual end-users and the potential users of the institutions' products and services will be protected from dubious actions and practices such as increment in interest rates, fraud, etc. which are all unfair practices. This will be done through disclosure publicly and transparency within the institutions' programs. The financial regulations also cover all financial services and national consumer protection legislation

and in their absence, the Apex bodies of microfinance institutions would be encouraged to work effectively to develop and implement the standards of the institution.

1.4.2.5 Data / Information Gathering and Dissemination

For microfinance to be effectively planned, monitored and evaluated as well as sustainable, there should be accurate, reliable, and timely collection of data and dissemination of information. This will call for a well-defined system to capture, storage, and disseminate information. This will be done at all levels to facilitate the institutions' operations and results. To enhance microfinance sub-sectors' activities, board members have the aims of having an organized system to help harmonize and gather information, processing it, and dissemination appropriately. Central database systems shall be accessible to all stakeholders and microfinance institutions association in Ghana would be made responsible for data processing which will be provided through microfinance apex bodies, making use of the MIX format as much as possible. At the national microfinance forum, research findings, data collection technique and data management aspects of the sub-sector are all issues and topics to be discussed.

2. RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Microfinance is an attempt for small depositors' access to financial services to be improved like access to savings, microcredit, and insurance for the active poor individuals/households who were not banking by the traditional banks. This means that the institution does not only offer product and services to low-income households and the poor people but also offers them with the opportunity to bank and have micro-savings, microcredit, and lending in groups which before these poor and low-income individuals were not having access too (Schreiner and Colombet, 2001). Microfinance which is also known as microcredit is a form of banking service rendered to poor people and low-income individuals or groups who are unemployed and also denied access to financial services. Again, the provision of financial and non-financial services to poor people, very poor self-employed people is termed as microfinance (Otere 1999).

Impact can be defined as the extent to which the life of microfinance institutions clients changed in terms of income and wealth (Conning 1999). The objective of the microcredit program indeed is to reduce poverty and to offer financial service to individuals who were not having access formally. Even though is seemingly difficult for the impact of service rendered to customers to be measured, there will be a direct or indirect impact on the welfare, conditions and living standard

of the poor which enable us to measure the performance of microfinance institutions. The impact of one institution/setup to the other can be a positive impact or negative impact. Under this study, impact of financial regulations and government policies on microfinance sector development in Ghana can either have a negative effects, positive effects or both effects on the institutions.

Financial regulations are laws and rules that governs financial institutions or are forms of regulations, supervision or monitoring that align financial institutions to some kind of principles, requirements, processes and procedures, guidelines, and restrictions aiming to maintain financial system integrity. These laws and restrictions imposed are mostly by the government financial regulators through the central bank of a particular country, a private body, or international group to protect the customers or investors' savings, to maintain markets order and to promote stability of financial markets. Financial regulations are mainly described to include six different kinds of controls/regulations which are employed to achieve different purposes. The categories of the financial regulations include Macroeconomic control, allocation control, structural control, prudential control, organizational control and protective controls/regulations (Vittas, 1992).

2.2 Empirical Review

A study conducted on the impact of regulation on profitability using cross-sectional data and analyzed using an econometric analysis by Mersland and Strom (2009) in their findings on these regulations on profitability, they found out that, regulation has an insignificant relationship on the performance of the institution. Evidence of outreach on a trade-off was never found. Arysad (2005) on their study microfinance institutions performance and sustainability in Indonesia using a village credit institution as a case study, found out that, an economy which is growing and supported by government policies in all part of their operations by providing a legal root for microfinance institutions has a higher performance and is more sustainable. That Central Bank regulations of the country had contributed towards the benefits and successes of microfinance institutions. There is the need for appropriate regulations of the subsector in the country and it should be supported by effective government policies to monitor and supervise the institutions to ensure long term sustainability and reduce collapse rate in the sector. This regulation and policy-making of the markets call for the active participation of government and regulators in the microfinance industry. The regulators believe that to protect the customers and their savings, the interest rate should be capped and transparency promoted. Pouchous (2012) said most of the microfinance management and professionals are against such practices. They are of the view that

the policymakers may not be able to come out with an appropriate interest rate cap which will help the development, sustainability, growth, and survival of microfinance institutions in Ghana which intend to jeopardize the services of the financial inclusion to the poor customers (Helms & Reille, 2004). Regulators can only be through the regulatory requirements to take account of microfinance loan pricing to protect the poor customer against harm and higher prices for this implies the macro level. This was the reason for the government intervention because the macroeconomic disruptions can have a consequence on financial institutions of the country as a whole. According to Arun & Murinde (2010), the main purpose of regulating the microfinance institutions is to ensure the efficiency, soundness, smoothness, and stability of financial services and to protect the consumers. Thus no activity of the microfinance institutions should harm the clients and the regulations not to affect the activities of the microfinance institutions and vice versa.

3. MINIMUM CAPITAL REQUIREMENT IN GHANA

Another term for minimum capital requirements is regulatory capital. It is the amount of capital/money that is required or demanded by bank of Ghana regulators for microfinance institutions to hold in their possession to operate. The reason for the capital requirement is to ensure that financial institutions and deposit institutions do not dominate their holdings with investments which can increase default risk. It also ensures that the institutions have enough funds to sustain their operating losses and still honoring customers' withdrawals.

Ghana case, a minimum capital requirement amount is 500, 000 Ghana cedi as of 2015. The amount was increased to 1000,000 Ghana cedi in 2017. In 2018, the minimum capital was increased to 2,000,000.00 Ghana cedi. In a press released organized by Bank of Ghana, the public was made aware of the closure of 347 microfinance institutions across Ghana and the reasons for the closure according to the Bank of Ghana include: breaches of corporate governance, diversion of clients/customers deposits to other private businesses, undercapitalization, poor lending and investment practices, and non-compliance with regulatory guidelines.

According to the speaker, it was based on the above reasons that, the Bank of Ghana is considering increasing the minimum capital requirement of the sub-sector which is currently GH¢2 million, to prevent the above financial crisis not to repeat soon. The press release also stated that “the regulators from the bank of Ghana are undertaking a comprehensive review of the entire financial regulations system through the review of monitoring and supervisory policies and regulatory directives, reviewing the licensing requirement, minimum capital requirement

reviewing for microfinance institutions and the possible consolidations encouragement of the industry through acquisition, mergers and acquisition willingly by the operators”.

An Economics Professor Peter Quartey, from the University of Ghana in an interviewed with him mentioned that the issue of the minimum capital increment is long overdue since its delay led to the alarming of many microfinance institutions that have no ability nor capability to operate and compete in the sub-sector. He further states that, “the microfinance institutions is kind of business/banking, and this type of banking means a serious business, some amount of capital is needed by the operators to support themselves so that the customers and the public donot lose confidence in their operations in case of any default or challenge for the institution”. According to him, a decent minimum capital should be offered to the industry so that those who cannot afford the amount, will leave for those with the capital required to remain". He told the Business and Financial Times (B&FT) in an interview.

3.1 Reserve Requirement in Ghana

Reserve Requirement is the minimum amount of capital a financial institution must hold in reserve based on their deposits. The term reserve requirement also sometimes referred to as cash reserve ratio is the minimum amount of cash or its cash equivalent that is computed as a percentage of its deposits which financial institution, example banks, microfinance institutions, other deposit-taking institutions (insurance companies, credit unions, savings & loans) are required lawfully to keep in their possession, which may not be used for investment or lending. The Reserve requirement is important because it serves as a safeguard for inordinate and sudden demands for cash withdrawal in case of bank runs. Also, it serves as a control mechanism for cash withdrawal from an economy or cash injecting (liquidity) into an economy. In Ghana, banks are expected to hold 9 percent of their deposits at the bank of Ghana as a primary reserve and are also required to hold a 15 percent of their deposits that are eligible to Bank of Ghana as a secondary reserve requirement as in medium-term and T-bills of the government of Ghana securities.

4. METHODOLOGY

This article was purely conducted to understand the perspective of the regulators, and policymakers on how effective the policies and regulations are to the beneficiaries and the microfinance institutions management about the impact of regulatory guidelines and government policies on their operations. Views on some of the institutions and individuals offering direct and indirect services to the microfinance institution were also sought on the dealings of the industry

and challenges towards the institutions. Qualitative interviews were conducted using a semi-structured interview guide to various respondents over seven weeks and follow up interviews were also conducted at a different time both through interviews (face-to-face), emails and on phone. To know financial regulations & government policies impact on the micro-financial sector of Ghana. This study brings on board the combined analyses of the regulatory framework and the policies implemented for the institutions involved. Related literature review of the microfinance institutions was examined, the policies implemented on the sub-sector was elaborated, and the regulatory guidelines and framework were analyzed with the objective of the article/study to evaluate and conclude on necessary measures to the institutions' growth, development, and sustainability. The review also discusses the challenges facing both the microfinance institutions and the financial regulations and these were discussed in detailed in the third article of this study.

With the sources of data, the relevant information/data for this article was organized through primary and secondary sources. Primarily, the government institutions and private institutions involved in the policymaking, regulations, and supervisions, rendering financial services, creation, formulation and implementations of the microfinance programs and policies were researched. These institutions include the Ministry of Finance, Bank of Ghana, Microfinance Institutions Network, Ghana Microfinance Companies, Microfinance and Small Loans Centers, and Microfinance Institutions. Secondarily, the Germany Development Cooperation (GTZ), Agricultural Development Bank (ADB) Ghana Statistical Service (GSS), Regional Institute for Population Studies (RIPs) through their websites and homepages were consulted, publications, press releases, individual contacts about microfinance, regulators, government policymakers on the sub-sector.

Interviews were conducted based on the interview guide presented in Annex A and focus group discussion guide for few management of microfinance institutions in Annex B. The interviews were conducted to solicit respondents' views on the policy-making and implementation of the microfinance institutions in the country and their general opinions on the subject matter. Also, information was gathered from the Bank of Ghana through an email sent to the bank's secretary to the financial regulations sector. The staff in charge of the microfinance institutions regulations and supervision answered the questions and was called on the phone later to rectify and clarify some of the given answers/responses.

Furthermore, the Focus Group Discussions with some selected management of the microfinance institutions was to get information on their views and opinions on the subject matter. A consensus was reached with the group of respondents on their opinions on each of the questions asked and the solutions they provided. This makes the discussions participatory and encouraging. Another secondary source of data was from published articles, finance books, research methods books, microfinance books, and the internet within the study area.

The sampling of the interviewees/respondents was done based on the convenience of the participants and the staff available to assist the researcher in the data gathering. In all, thirty-two (32) interviews were conducted using structured interview guides and 3 different focus group discussions to the various microfinance institutions' management at their convenient time and on their approval to be interviewed. Pseudonym and acronyms were used instead of the names of the respondents for confidentiality reasons. The data or respondent responses were analyzed qualitatively using a thematic analysis.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Response to First Research Question

1. What are the positive impacts of regulations & policies on microfinance operations?

The findings from this research have provided the answer to the above research question:

The respondents from Ministry of Finance (MOF), Bank of Ghana (BOG), Ghana Microfinance Company (GAMC), Ghana Microfinance Institutions Network (GHAMFIN) staff and management of various Microfinance Institutions were asked the above question on regulations and policies of microfinance institutions and the below is their responses:

“A male respondent from the bank of Ghana financial regulation section by name Kofi who graduated from the University of Ghana, 48years old and married said: “There are a lot more positive impacts of financial regulations on microfinance sector development in Ghana. Kofi mentioned monitoring the sector and supervising them by bank of Ghana makes the regulators know the institutions performing well and those lacking expertise knowledge, facing financial challenges, and liquidity issues. He further mentioned that the microfinance sector in the country, the majority of them are working on debt and cannot pay their customers today in case of closedown and it was due to regular monitoring and supervision that the regulators realized this. He again mentioned that the regulatory framework and guidelines of the institutions help the financial regulators to know the serious microfinance institutions in terms of their reporting strategies and performance levels”.

Madam Abena, a 43-year-old woman, who holds a Master's degree from Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology in Business Administration, Finance option in charge of the non-banking financial institution at the bank of Ghana, regulatory and supervision section during a telephone interviewed with her mentioned that:

“Financial regulation in the country has a lot more positive impacts on the institutions. The clients/customers that bank with the institutions enjoy positive impacts from the regulations of the sector. Abena said, regulations underpin the markets, help protect the rights and the safety of the customers in the microfinance institutions, ensures delivering of quality products and services to the clients, and again helps in addressing the smoothness, safety, viability, soundness and stability of financial institutions as well as the entire financial system, payment systems, to achieve more market-oriented framework, regulatory measures, and policies”.

The staff of the Ministry of Finance were interviewed on the above research question and below were some of their answers.

According to H. A. of a graduate from the University for Development Studies at the ministry of finance, Financial Sector Division, the policy-making body of a microfinance institution in Ghana said in an interview with her both on the telephone and an interview guide sent to her through email explains that:

“The regulation helps to reduce the public outcry due to the frequent and continues folding up of the institutions in the country. H. A mentioned that the rate at which the microfinance industry is collapsing in the country, most of the institutions getting their licenses been revoked by Bank of Ghana, majority of them are insolvent, some ceased operations due to insolvency and poor performances and all these affect the customer of the institutions more than the management”.

“H.A again said the regulations have a positive impact in that, it comes in to help in the protection of the customers and their deposits. That, most of the management is doing what they want with the customers' monies and the regulations and the supervisions now is checking what is done with the raised funds from the institutions. H.A. opined that, as part of the customers protections and long term survival and sustainability of the microfinance institution, the bank of Ghana increase the minimum paid-up capital that is capital requirement to help reduce the collapse rate of the institutions and in case of collapse, those amounts can be used to help the clients of the institution. She said I think the advantages of regulations far outweigh the disadvantages narrates HA”.

Besides, H.A, Mr. A.K at the policy formulation and implementation section of the ministry of finance, financial sector division mentioned during the field data collection that:

“Regulations in Ghana have both positive and negative impacts on microfinance in Ghana. That is a mixture of good and bad but if the right things will be done by the regulators possibly the goodness of it will outweigh the bad side of it. Yet still, most of them think its better for microfinance institutions to be regulated in the country. He states the positive

impact of regulations on microfinance institutions to include: 1. Regulations help shape microfinance institutions and 2. Regulations made the microfinance institutions to stick to their core mandate”. He further explains the above points as:

This is because without regulations most management would have managed the institutions in their best interest instead of the interest of the customers first and the entire employees. Regulations help put all managers on track to act towards the guidelines, rules, principles, and regulations of the bank of Ghana regulatory framework. The regulations have guidelines and frameworks that every microfinance institution should follow and work accordingly. These regulatory guidelines are effective and the institutions that act outside it attract some penalties by the regulators. Also, the policies help protect the customers and microfinance institutions”.

Furthermore, the regulations from the bank of Ghana made the microfinance institutions to stick to their core mandate and do only what they were registered to do. Some microfinance institutions owners and management go beyond their core values and exceed what they were registered by the registrar general's department to do as an institution. Because regulations are available, monitoring and supervising the activities of the institutions, the managers find it difficult to easily deviate from their core values since the deviation is what mostly leads the institutions to default and go bankrupt”.

During the focus group discussion with the staff and management of Afro-Arab microfinance institution in Accra Newtown, they are of the view that, financial regulation has a lot of impacts on microfinance institution in the country and that, the regulations has contributed immensely towards the success, maintenance, and development of the microfinance sector. They mentioned the positive impacts of financial regulations on microfinance institutions to include:

- Training the staff of microfinance institutions.
- Capacity building of the management and other employees of MFIs.
- Monitoring and supervision of the microfinance sub-sector
- Advice and counseling on records keeping, finances and loans
- Withdrawal of licensed from non-functioning or bad performing and insolvent institutions

The above was explained by the management as:

“The regulators train the employees of the microfinance institution on reporting standards and other key issues about reporting to them. The training is done in groups with other microfinance institutions either monthly, quarterly, semiannually or annually. The training helps the staff to know other financial and accounting standards that they have no idea of before the training. Also, the regulators help build the capacity of the microfinance employees. The focus is more on human capacity building and this leads to other abilities and capabilities enhanced”.

“Again, the monitoring and supervising of the institutions make the management and other staff to work diligently and effectively towards achieving the purpose of the organization and following the rules and regulations laid down to them by the regulators”.

“Furthermore, advice and counseling to the management and employees on what is right and expected of the institution is one of the good aspects of the financial regulators said another respondent. They advise on issues of finances, credit management, recruitment, and accounting principles. Upon all these any institutions that deviate from the rules and regulation is sanction and it depends on the gravity of the offense, it can lead to close down or withdrawal of the institution's license”.

We observed from the field data collections that, a lot of positive factors of financial regulations on microfinance institutions were mentioned by the respondents. The mentioned and explained factors above are a few of the positive impacts of regulations mentioned during the interviews and discussions.

5.2 Response to Second Research Question

What are the negative impacts of regulations and policies on microfinance institutions' operations?

Aside from discussing the positive impact of regulations on microfinance institutions in the country, the institution is not without negative impacts. Some of the negative effects of regulations on microfinance institutions mentioned by the respondents are indicated below:

“Maltiti of Dahinsheli" Microfinance Institutions in Tamale, who is an accounting and finance manager, a married man and a Higher National Diploma holder from Tamale Technical University was asked in an interview with him what are the negative impacts of regulations to microfinance institutions in the country, below are some of his responses:

“The regulations have some negative impacts on our institutions. Some of this negative impact from my thinking is: Increment in the minimum capital requirement, the reporting standards and procedures of the microfinance institutions to the regulators, revocation of some microfinance institutions licensed by Bank of Ghana regulators, which leads to the collapse of most MFIs in the country”.

“The manager Mr. Maltiti complained about the increment in the minimum capital requirement of more than 100 percent. He said this will not sustain the institutions but rather collapse most of the institutions in the country. He recommends that minimum capital should be done based on cases and according to the area of establishment and the number of customers each institution is serving. The Return on Equity (ROE) of the institution and the Return on Asset (ROA) of the institutions must be considered before making this general rule and passing it through”.

Maltiti again said, the sales, expenses, growth, profitability, number of customers served, numbers of staff, and location of the microfinance institutions all vary from one institution

to the other. So generalizing minimum paid-up capital is unfair to most microfinance institutions in the country”.

Madam Cecelia, a 27-year-old staff at the microfinance institution in Techiman a mother and the confident woman mentioned that, all other staff of different microfinance institutions are complaining about the minimum capital requirement increment.

"Cecelia concluded that most of the microfinance institutions may not be operating at the end of the year based on what Bank of Ghana is expecting from them. They wish they could change the required amount but it is beyond their ability and capability. Cecelia further reports that all the staff of the institutions now are looking for job opportunities elsewhere because the probability of them being jobless at the end of the year is high due to the high demands from regulators and Government from the microfinance institutions as require reserve and minimum capital requirement”.

Mr. Atto a Higher National Diploma holder from Accra Technical University and a manager at the Ghana microfinance institutions network opined that:

“The effect of financial regulations on microfinance institutions is the fact that some of the regulators lack the knowledge of regulation and they the management when it comes to submitting reports, monitoring and evaluating the microfinance sub-sector. He again mentioned that the number of regulators in the country as compared to the number of microfinance in Ghana is very small, due to these, not all the sub-sector gets monitoring /regulation from the bank of Ghana regulators. Ato is of the view that, if the regulators are many and the powers of the regulators decentralized, then regulators in the country can have a continuously positive impact on microfinance institutions and not negative impacts”.

The researchers observed that most of the institutions complaining about the minimum capital requirement set out by the regulators of Bank of Ghana and the government of Ghana are the institution that could not afford the needed amount by the due date set. The majority of them were scared of taking over, acquisition, mergers and complete shut down by the end of the year due to bank of Ghana directives indicated to them. Again most of the staff of the various institution wish the government will come in to support the microfinance institutions due to their contribution to the economic development of the country.

5.3 Response to Third Research Question

What are the roles of Government policies towards microfinance institutions operations and development?

During the interview, respondents from the bank of Ghana said: Ministry of Finance, the financial sector division is the department in charge of microfinance institution policy-

making and implementations in the country. The role of the department at the ministry in the microfinance sub-sector include:

“Creating a viable policy environment, macroeconomic environment, and microenvironment for microfinance sector growth and development in the country.

In charge of policy formulation and implementation of microfinance institutions. In charge of giving directions and in collaboration with key stakeholders of the sub-sector, and

The policy-making body at the Finance Ministry established a forum for microfinance institutions.

He further opined that they again work hand in hand with other Ministries, Departments, and Agencies, aside from the MDAs, policy-making body also work with some different key stakeholder and relevant institutions to help regulate, supervise, monitor, direct, guide and evaluate all microfinance institution activities in the country. Furthermore, the institution is in charge of coordinating all assistance from donors and development partners to the sub-sector. For example, financial and technical assistance, financial resources are all directed to the institution”.

Uncle Ebo, a 44-year-old married man from GHAMFIN, who holds a Master's degree in micro-financing in an interviewed with him mentioned the role of the microfinance policy to include the following:

“They serve as middlemen between the regulators and the microfinance institutions. They collaborate with key stakeholders towards achieving the purpose, goals, aims, and objectives of the sub-sector. Policymakers help both the regulators and microfinance institutions and the protection of borrowers, small depositors, the clients and consumers of a microfinance institution in the country. He finally said policymakers serve as checks and balances or watchdogs between the regulators and the microfinance sub-sector”.

A 52 old man Mr. Sammy at the ministry of finance, financial sector division in charge of microfinance policy making and implementation answered the above question:

“Sammy mentioned the roles to include, protecting the customers, organizing training programs to the microfinance staffs, building the capacity of the management, act in between the regulators and the microfinance institutions, ensuring the progress of the institutions to long term sustainability”.

"Sammy further narrates that, the finance ministry, particularly this section called FSD, thus financial services division, makes sure that, the institution work to serve their purposes of bridging the gap between the rich and poor through poverty reduction, employment creation and empowerment is ensured. Also to protect the customers since it is their funds that are been used in running the institution. He said again that, the microfinance institutions are working in line with the poverty reduction strategies objective of the country, so we ensure that, the right thing is done by both the microfinance management and the financial regulators”.

Gladys a 32 old year single staff at the ministry of finance policy-making body and implementation in an interviewed with her with an interview guide mentioned the roles of the government policies towards microfinance institutions operations and development as:

“Creating a viable and sound financial policy environment, macroeconomic environment, and microeconomic environment for the growth and accelerated development of the microfinance institution in the county, and being in charge of all policy formulation of the institution and directions in collaboration with interested parties/stakeholders of the institution”.

Simon an intelligent and confident looking staff from Ghana Microfinance Company who is married with kids, 36-year-old gentleman narrates that:

“Microfinance forums are being established and managed by the policy-making body at the Ministry of Finance. Policymakers also work in collaboration with other Ministries, Departments, and Agencies, including other bodies and stakeholders to help in monitoring, guiding, supervising and evaluating all microfinance sub-sector activities in the country”.

Issac from the ministry of finance also said the role of the office that is the policy-making unit of the microfinance subsector cannot be overemphasized. Several roles are been played by the sector to ensure that, the microfinance institution and the other stakeholders involved in the institutions work together for effective and efficient quality services rendered. He mentioned that:

“The institution (policy-making) coordinates all the assistance that comes from the development partners and other donors. That is, the assistance/support in the form of a financial assistant, technical assistant and the financial resources all are harmonized and directed to the microfinance sub-sector. Finally, he said the fund activities and programs of the microfinance institutions are been overseen by the policymakers and the implementation body of the finance ministry in the country”.

The researchers observed from the responses and discussions that, the policy-making body and the implementation of the microfinance institutions in the country have a lot offering to the institutions both to the regulators and the microfinance sub-sector. As in whether the aims and purpose of the sector have been achieved is the next discussion.

5.4 Response to Fourth Research Question

What are the Objectives of Government Policies towards Microfinance Institutions in Ghana?

The respondents were asked what they think are the objectives of the government policies to the microfinance industry in the country and the following were their narrations for the question.

According to Madam H.A, of the Ministry of Finance, financial sector division in a telephone interview and through an email sent to her with an attached interview guide, she states the objective of the government policies to microfinance institution to include:

“The sector help create a viable, sound, and enabling environment at all levels (highest and lowest levels), which supports the activities, programs, and the operations of the microfinance industry in the country.

Furthermore, H.A narrates that, the policy-making body provides facilities for the microfinance sector's sustainable free flow of capital, development of financial and human capital, and adequate infrastructure in Ghana.

Again, policies for the sector ensure a well-coordinated, organized, and harmonized microfinance sub-sector within Ghana’s financial system.

Also, policymakers are ensuring a sound, stable, integrated, smooth, and very sustainable microfinance institution and financial system which targets and reaches active poor and low-income individuals in the country”.

Finally, H.A narrates that, “financial sector division in charge of policymaking for the government in the country ensures and facilitates the protection of consumers or customers" and the small depositors of the microfinance institutions”.

5.5 Response to Fifth Research Question

What Contributions do Regulations and Policies have on Microfinance Sector Development in the Country?

The contribution of financial regulations and government policies to the microfinance sector development of the country are those listed and explained below according to the interviewees/respondents from the various interviews conducted by microfinance institutions management, regulators, and policymakers. The following are the contributions from their narrations:

Hajia a graduate from the University of Ghana, married and very confident women from the ministry of Finance narrates:

“Hajia explains that one of the contributions is by taking regular reports from the microfinance institutions. Reports taking by the regulators, monthly, quarterly, semiannually and yearly help the microfinance sub-sector to keep their records correctly and report to the regulators as in when it is needed. Without regulations, some of the institutions may not have kept and maintain records of a week, month nor yearly. It is one of the regulatory requirements by the Bank of Ghana for the institutions they supervise to submit to them the monthly report for evaluation and analysis. Through the reports, they can easily see faults/mistake and demand for answers from the institutions management for the necessary correction to be done”. The policymakers also support and guide the dealings of the microfinance institutions, train the staff, build the capacity of the management, and organize

seminars and programs for the institutions to discuss issues of concerns and interest to the institutions Hajia narrates”.

Abbass a 41-year-old gentleman from Koforidua Technical University and a long term serving the staff of Ghana Association of Microfinance Company mentioned that:

"Regulations and policies help the aims and objectives of the microfinance institution to be realized through intensive monitoring and supervisions".

"From the field findings, the regulators made mentioned that, because of their regulations, rules, monitoring, supervision, and the guidelines for the institutions, most of the microfinance institutions management do proper work and this makes their work easier. Again, when most of the management heard of the regulators coming to monitor them, they do all that is expected of them before they were questioned or queried and this makes their work of monitoring and supervising easier and helpful”.

In a focus group discussion with the management of “Dahinsheli Microfinance institution” in Tamale, the respondents mentioned that: regulations and policies are there to protect the customers because they are dealing with their monies:

“SS, a staff of the above institution mentioned that another contribution of regulators and the policymakers to the microfinance sector development in the country is the protection of the customers. The customers also attested to that likewise the microfinance institutions employees. Because of the protection, most customers feel secured to deal with the institutions. Clients are protected against fraudulent products and bad services. Their savings and investments all are protected by the regulators hence the need for a minimum capital requirement and liquidity reserves. So that in the case of the institution's default, those monies can be relied on”.

“Again, there are field inspections by the regulators to the institutions. Both announced and unannounced to check the information the management supplies them with. Due to the unannounced inspection and monitoring by the regulators, the managements are always on track and doing what is expected of them at the right time Chelpang narrates”.

Mr. Doe a member of the focus group discussion mentioned that, the regulators and policymakers serve as checks-and-balances to the microfinance institutions:

“Also, the managers of some institutions responded that the regulators and the policymakers' serve as checks and balances to them. They are always checking on what they do and at what time they doing what. This made them not to involve in any activity they were not registered to do. Engaging in any unregistered to do products and services can lead to a collapse of an institution and because of the checks and balances, we are afraid to be involved in those activities”.

Sadat, a 29 old HND graduate, an accounting manager of the institution narrates the institutions' contribution to microfinance institutions has:

“He explains that another contribution of the policymakers and the regulators to the microfinance sector development that we cannot be silent about is the support the microfinance institution receives from the institutions' example, they give technical support, train us on how to submit prudential reports, and help build our capacity. This helps to build most of the management and other staff. Sometimes they support financially. Another training they give to the microfinance institutions which helps them most is training on financial inclusion and collateral registry reporting training explained by Sadat”.

Nasara, a female staff of the institution, a graduate from Tamale Technical University narrates that:

“Regarding the minimum capital requirement, some microfinance respondents said, the regulators and policymakers speak on their behalf. That they are trying their best to see what can be done about it. So both the regulators, government, policymakers and other key stakeholders of the microfinance institution are negotiating to see what will be the best outcome Nasara”.

We observed from the respondents' responses that, some of the contributions mentioned are repeated by other staff. Some of the answers are key and almost all respondents are mentioning it. Zee a married woman from MASLOC concluded that regulations and policies help improve the performance of the institutions. According to her:

“The performance of the microfinance institutions also increased due to the regulations and policies imposed on them said a branch manager at MASLOC. The regulations made them work effectively and efficiently toward achieving their goals and objectives and reporting standards. It helps shape the organization and the workers. It also helps increase the profit margin and increase sales level. Both length and breadth of outreach are increased and this increase the sub-sectors shares and also performance improved Zee explains”.

Alhaji, a manager, experienced staff, and a matured married man at the Baobab microfinance institution in Tamale reported that:

“The, regulations and policies made them comply with rules and regulations and follow the regulatory guidelines and requirements. That for them to continue being in operations for a longer period, they must comply with the laws and rules including the laid down procedures of regulation. Failure to do so leads to appropriate sanctions. Due to this, regulators and policymakers, they help microfinance institutions to survive and to be sustainable”.

5.6 Responses to some Questions on the Interview Guides and FGDs

What is the Role of Financial Regulations to the Ghanaian Economy?

According to the respondents, the role of financial regulations/regulators cannot be overemphasized. The operations of financial systems through financial regulations, monitoring,

and supervision are influenced by policies yet still, the financial regulations perform a key role in the financial institutions as well as the financial system of the entire country. Below are some of the roles of financial regulations as mentioned by the participants:

- The regulators give the institutions rules and guidelines to follow and to operate with.
- The microfinance institutions were made to send monthly, quarterly, semiannually and annual returns to the regulators for evaluation.
- Regulators make microfinance institutions keep some monies with other Banks in the country.
- The regulators protect customers' deposits, savings, and investment.
- The liquidity ratio of the microfinance institutions is been accessed by the regulators.
- Regulators monitor the core activities of the microfinance institutions: weekly, monthly, quarterly
- Announced and unannounced monitoring to monitor the performance of the institutions and to correct deviations by giving proper guidelines and directions.

5.7 What are the Duties and Responsibilities of Financial Regulators to Microfinance Institutions?

The respondents indicated below as the duties and responsibilities of financial regulators to the microfinance sector in the country.

- Regulators served as checks and balances on the microfinance sub-sector.
- Regulators do organize training to the microfinance institutions: For example, (training on Loans, Information Technology, customer service, and customer protection).
- The Bank of Ghana regulators ensures that the right thing is done by the microfinance institutions to help make the institutions sustainable.
- Regulators help microfinance institutions to get into financial inclusion.

5.8 What are the Advantages of Policy Making body to Microfinance Institutions?

From the findings, the respondents said: the Ministry of Finance, financial sector division is the department in charge of microfinance institution policy-making and implementations. The role of the department at the ministry in the microfinance sub-sector and their advantages include:

- Creating enabling financial policy environment & macroeconomic environment for survival and accelerated development of the microfinance institution in the county.

- In charge of all policy formulation of the institution and directions in collaboration with interested parties of the institution.
- Microfinance forums are being established and managed by the policy-making body at the Finance Ministry
- Policymakers also work in collaboration with other Ministries, Departments, and Agencies, including other stakeholders to help monitor the activities, supervises and evaluates all microfinance/sub-sector activities in the country.
- Again, policymakers coordinate all supports and external assistance from development partners and donors. Thus, support like financial support, technical and financial resources are all directed to the institution.
- Finally, the microfinance fund activities are also overseen by the policy-making body.

6. DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS

From the findings, we observed that policies and regulations in the country have a strong impact on microfinance sector development. This is because policymakers help the institutions by building their capacity and organizing training programs for them which boost their knowledge and skills and also helps in the long term sustainability of the microfinance institutions. Regulations in the country have an impact on the microfinance sector development because they regulate the institutions and make sure that they follow the regulatory guidelines and principles and send their financial and accounting reporting monthly, quarterly and annually. These make the management and staff work diligently to meet the standards and demands of the regulators.

Again, the policy formulators work hand in hand with the regulators of Bank of Ghana, the various microfinance institutions in the country and other stakeholders of the institution by coordinating and collaborating the affairs of the institutions. This helps in the flow and dissemination of information and the necessary amendments and directions are given at the right time. The microfinance institutions respondents mentioned that some of the policies and regulations implemented in the institutions are so rigid and needs amendments and update because it is affecting their performance and leads most of the microfinance sub-sector to a collapse.

According to the regulators, most of the microfinance institutions do not comply with the regulatory guidelines and principles and this is making it difficult for them when regulating and supervising them. They again mentioned that recently most microfinance institutions' licenses were temporarily seized due to poor performance and disobedience of the rules and regulations

from regulators. It was again indicated that, the policies coordinates the affairs of all the microfinance stakeholders and brings them on board to help the effective functioning of the institutions.

In furtherance of the above, the regulators mentioned why there was an increment in the minimum capital requirement by bank of Ghana regulators that most of the microfinance institutions were having dubious aims of running with the clients' savings and so if the bank of Ghana is having possession of that amount, some of the customers can be saved. Finally, most management uses the depositor's savings for illegal and unethical businesses that end up collapsing and not able to refund the depositors their savings. The increment aims to protect the customers and their savings.

7. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that regulations and policies are a very important aspect of microfinance institutions in Ghana and without them, most of the microfinance institutions management will have only work to serve their own interest.

Again, though microfinance institutions in Ghana keep on increasing day in day out, yet still the collapsing rate is alarming. This calls for proper regulations, monitoring, and supervision, and also effective policies in place to sustain the institutions. All the institutions interviewed in Ghana during the field data collection complained about the minimum capital requirement been increased by bank of Ghana to be high and very difficult for most of them to be able to raise that amount and this will also make it difficult for new entries into the sub-sector.

Furthermore, it was indicated that microfinance played a vital role by supporting the growth and development of the financial institutions, increasing the banking population thus, financial inclusion, increasing number of savings and investments in the country, and help in the training and capacity building in the financial sector and these are targeted towards economic development, hence the need for its proper regulations to continue to support the financial system, economic development by increasing financial inclusion.

More so, the government policies towards the microfinance sub-sector as part of their objective has helped and protected the marginalized group: comprising the women, children, youth and the underprivileged people in the country. For a more positive impact to be realized among the poor, and for the betterment in their lives, microfinance policy should be coordinated with other national policies.

Additionally, the issue of minimum capital and microfinance close down will make lots of the working staff jobless while increasing unemployment rate in the country. This calls the need for bank of Ghana to ensure reasonable and practical minimum capital which will help create more employment, increase outreach, soundness and improved standards.

Also, financial regulation mostly failed in the country due to regulators focus on the risk of a single institution and not on systematic risk. They fail to see many microfinance sectors taking an aggressive risk and no proper risk management. The framework of regulations in Ghana was inappropriate because it does not monitor financial products and services including their operations hence the sub-sector takes lots of risks daily and no proper risk management by the institutions.

We expect the regulators to do better in Ghana and need regulatory reforms which will help bring stable and sound financial market, protect the consumers, clients, investors, borrowers and which is transparent to improve and help restore confidence in the microfinance and financial sector at large.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

The issue of the minimum capital requirements should be considered by the bank of Ghana and the necessary amendments made. It should be a case by case bases and not generalized. The bank of Ghana should be independent of the institutions to license, regulate, supervise, train, monitor closely and evaluate all microfinance institutions in the country. Also, the policies for the microfinance sector from the policymakers can be integrated with other policies such as the development agency policies, the poverty reduction policy and programs to avoid many policy conflicts in the microfinance sub-sector in the country.

Furthermore, the policymaking and implementation body should work diligently to include all key stakeholders for the effective implementation of the policies and that, Apex bodies should be engaged in decision making regarding regulations, monitoring, supervision, policy implementation and operations of the institutions. It was again recommended that, microfinance institutions should be handled by a separate office not bank of Ghana and this body should be based at the regional levels in order to educate, train and equip the management and staffs of microfinance institutions in all the ten (10) Regions of the country on microfinance accounting and reporting standards, financial management so as to ensure correct and timely reporting of events to be able to improve performance and standards.

Then again, regulators should ensure that all unregistered microfinance institutions in the country are shut down since they are those increasing the collapse rate of the sector. The unlicensed institutions should also be made to follow the necessary procedures in registering and licensing the institutions in the country or their licenses revoked by bank of Ghana. There is the need for bank of Ghana to come out with full-fledge laws and regulations solely for microfinance institutions in the country. Finally, the work of the Ghana Association of Microfinance Institutions Network (GHAMFIN) and advice on microfinance institutions activities must be taken into consideration and credit given to the institution.

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APPENDIXES

Annex- A: Interview Guide for Policymakers, Regulators and Microfinance Institutions Managers:

A: Demography

Name (pseudonym name)

Gender of Respondents (Male / Female)

Please what is your Age (15-25), (25-35), (35-45), (45-Above)

Your Level of Education please (SHS), (Diploma / HND), (Bachelor), (Masters), (Ph.D.)

Please, your marital status. A. (Married), b. (Singled), c. (Separated), d. (Living Together)

B: Main Questions

1. Why Regulate and Supervise Microfinance Institutions?
2. What are the Microfinance Policies and Programs in Ghana?
3. Please, what are the Rationale for Microfinance Policy in Ghana?
4. Can you please state the objectives of Microfinance Policy?
5. Please any Strategies to help achieve the Goals and Objectives?
6. What are the positive impacts of regulations & policies on microfinance operations?
7. What are the negative impacts of regulations and policies on microfinance institutions' operations?
8. What are the roles of Government policies towards microfinance institutions operations and development?
9. What are the objectives of government policies towards microfinance institutions in Ghana?
10. What contributions do regulations and policies have on microfinance sector development in the Country?
11. What is the role of financial regulations to the Ghanaian Economy?
12. What are the duties and responsibilities of financial regulators to microfinance institutions?
13. What are the advantages of policy making body to microfinance institutions?
14. Any measures by the government you think to help improve the microfinance sector?
15. What other recommendations do you have for the Institutions?

Thank you for your patience, time and responses.

Annex-B: Focus Group Discussion Guide For Microfinance Institutions Management

1. What are the positive impacts of regulations & policies on microfinance operations?
2. What are the negative impacts of regulations and policies on microfinance institutions' operations?

3. What are the roles of Government policies towards microfinance institutions operations and development?
4. What are the objectives of government policies towards microfinance institutions in Ghana?
5. What contributions do regulations and policies have on microfinance sector development in the Country?
6. What is the role of financial regulations to the Ghanaian Economy?
7. What are the duties and responsibilities of financial regulators to MFIs?
8. What are the advantages of policy making body to microfinance institutions?
9. Why Regulate and Supervise Microfinance Institutions?
10. What are the Microfinance Policies and Programs in Ghana?
11. Please, what are the Rationale for Microfinance Policy in Ghana?
12. Can you please state the objectives of Microfinance Policy?
13. What impacts do Regulations and Policies have on the microfinance sector?
14. What role does the Microfinance institution play in Ghana?
15. Any comment/suggestion to the government, policymakers or the institutions?

Thank you for your patience, time and responses.

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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